

MAIN FEATURES OF SMALL BUSINESS SUPPORT AND DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATION ACTIVITY IN WORLD EXPERIENCE.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13938321>

Annotatsiya: This article talks about how important the development of small business and private entrepreneurship is in today's developing world. An analysis was conducted on several foreign literatures regarding the importance of state regulation of small business and entrepreneurship to entrepreneurial activity. The main goal of our research is to apply foreign experiences in the regulation and development of small business and entrepreneurship. Secondary data was used to explain the research. Secondary source information was collected from internationally recognized databases and journals, articles, scientific articles, website information and official documents.

Key words: infrastructure, empirical research, improvement, capital, small business, resource, inclusive economic growth, potential customer.

Economic and social factors have a significant impact on the formation and development of small businesses shows. Small business success depends on the availability of capital, access to markets and skills availability of manpower plays an important role. In terms of capital, small businesses often has limited resources to invest in its business operations. Capital lack of it hinders their growth opportunities, their ability to innovate may hinder and limit market access.

It is known that the form of small and medium-sized business has established itself in the experience of today's developed countries with its high and successful results, and in some countries its share in the gross product is 60-70 percent. In the conditions of global economic integration, the implementation of deep structural changes and systematic reforms in the economy, and the private entrepreneur is a factor of ensuring sustainable economic growth lik (KBXT) is growing in importance. According to the data, "In China, 81.4 percent of the employed population and 54.3 percent of the gross domestic product (GDP), in Japan, approximately 70.8 percent of the employed population and 67.0 percent of the gross domestic product, in the United States, 50.6 percent of the employed population and 53.1 percent of the gross domestic product are allocated to small business" the development of unity in the economy Creating favorable opportunities for competitive environment will increase the state budget revenues. That is why all developed countries strive to support small business and private entrepreneurship under any circumstances. The economic indicators of small business and private entrepreneurship of foreign countries are much higher than those of developing countries. Our main goal in carrying out this research is to study the research carried out in this field by developed countries in the state regulation of small business and entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan, and to apply the lessons learned from their experience to Uzbekistan. It is not for nothing that we proudly call it Uzbekistan. Because the reforms implemented 5-6 years ago under this new name are aimed at arousing people's interest in new fields, making everyone able to create innovations in the direction they are

interested in, and most importantly, for everyone to try their luck in entrepreneurship. allows. In this regard, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his 2019 Address to the Supreme Council, said, "Truly, we can achieve progress and a prosperous life only through active entrepreneurship, tireless work and striving." According to the Decree on additional measures to ensure the rapid development of private property, comprehensive protection of private property and qualitative improvement of the business environment reduction, ensuring the early prevention of violations, increasing the effectiveness of their prevention and violations strengthens non-arbitration as the most important priority and the first-level task of state bodies.

Foreign countries have a carefully developed system of comprehensive support for small businesses, which ensures the globalization of the economy and sustainable development of the world financial and economic environment. As a result of these reforms, according to general calculations, business entities in developed countries make up more than 90 percent of the total number of enterprises, and employ more than 50 percent of the working population. means that the mechanism is fully developed. A number of measures have been developed in connection with the large-scale development of small business enterprises of economically developed countries and financial support for their innovative activities.

In conclusion, the main directions of entrepreneurship support in the conditions of the new Uzbekistan are of decisive importance in the development of the entrepreneurship ecosystem. By creating a favorable business environment, encouraging the adoption of innovation and technology, providing access to financial resources and training opportunities, and focusing on the implementation of effective policies and regulations, Uzbekistan will unleash the creativity and dynamism of its aspiring entrepreneurs. has the potential to give. With the joint efforts of the government and the private sector, entrepreneurship can become a powerful driving force of economic growth, creation of new jobs and social development in the country. As Uzbekistan continues on the path of economic reform and modernization, it is necessary to give priority to support of entrepreneurship as a means of fully opening entrepreneurial talents.

The digital revolution is changing the entire world society, as well as our lives is changing at an unprecedented speed. Of course, these changes are great opportunities not only that, but also creates great difficulties. Development of digital economy The creation of new technologies will make an important contribution to achieving the goal, however, a thousand percentage positive results are not guaranteed. Bringing the digital economy to small business sectors will facilitate work and causes development. Full coverage of the business class with digital technologies is one of the important issues today.

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